

Table: Ground-Based Intercept (GBI) Intercept Tests

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	Date	Test Name ^a	Kill Vehicle Type	Outcome ^b	Interceptor Launch Location, Local Time	Cost (millions USD)	Decoys/Notes
1	1999-Oct 2	IFT-3	Prototype	✓	K 2:22 pm		1 LB + (possibly) MSLS
2	2000-Jan 19	IFT-4	Prototype	✗	K 2:39 pm		KV sensor cooling failure
3	2000-Jul 8	IFT-5	Prototype	✗	K 4:39 pm		KV failed to separate
4	2001-July 1	IFT-6	Prototype	✓	K 3:02 pm		1 LB + MSLS
5	2001-Dec 1	IFT-7	Prototype	✓	K 3:19 pm		1 LB + MSLS
6	2002-Mar 2	IFT-8	Prototype	✓	K 2:31 pm		1 LB + 2 SB
7	2002-Oct 14	IFT-9	Prototype	✓	K 2:22 pm		1 LB + 2 SB
8	2002-Dec 11	IFT-10	Prototype	✗	K 8:46 pm		Night launch, but KV did not separate.
9	2004-Dec 15	IFT-13c	Prototype	✗	K 6:01 pm		Interceptor failed to launch

10	2005-Feb 14	IFT-14	Prototype	X	K < 6:42 pm		Interceptor failed to launch
11	2006-Sep 1	FTG-02	CE-I	✓ / X ^c	V 10:39 am		No decoys
	2007-May 25	FTG-03	CE-I	No Test	----		-----
12	2007-Sep 28	FTG-03a	CE-I	✓	V 1:18 pm		No decoys
13	2008-Dec 5	FTG-05	CE-I	✓	V 12:23 pm	\$210	Balloon decoys failed to deploy
14	2010-Jan 31	FTG-06	CE-II	X	V 3:46 pm	\$236/ \$310	KV guidance failure + SBX radar failure
15	2010-Dec 15	FTG-06a	CE-II	X	V 12:03 pm	\$360	KV guidance error
16	2013-Jul 5	FTG-07	CE-I	X	V ~11:30 am ^d	\$214	KV failed to separate
17	2014-Jun 22	FTG-06b	CE-II	✓	V 12:57 pm	\$269	2 balloons + FBS
18	2017-May 30	FTG-15	CE-II Block 1	✓	V Daytime ^e	\$244	First ICBM-range target. FBS + probably 1 SB
19	2019-Mar 25	FTG-11	CE-II Block 1 CE-II	✓	V 10:30 am	\$210.2	Salvo launch separated by less than 1 minute at ICBM target. Second interceptor hit intended non-

							warhead object (possibly a decoy?).
20	2023- Dec 11	FTG-12	CE-II Block 1	✓	V 6:38 am		GBI used in two-stage mode. IRBM target launched by C-17 aircraft.

No Test = Target failed and interceptor was not launched.

^a “IFT”: Integrated Flight Test, tests of elements of the GMD system, used prototype interceptors. “FTG”: Flight Test GMD, using operationally-configured interceptors. All tests are developmental, except for FTG-15 and FTG-11, which were operational tests.

^b The green check mark signifies that the KV was launched and intercept(s) were achieved as intended. The red X signifies that no intercept was achieved due to one or more failure modes.

^c = MDA scores FTG-02 as a “hit” but DOT&E scores it as a “no kill” because the EKV only achieved a “glancing blow.”

^d = Possibly plus or minus one hour

^e = Both target and interceptor were launched during daytime as shown on video.

Interceptor launch sites: K = Kwajalein Atoll V = Vandenberg Air Force Base

Test costs may not reflect costs incurred after test, such as data analysis or failure review

Decoys:

LB = large spherical balloon, brighter than warhead target

SB = small spherical balloon, dimmer than warhead target

FBS = final booster stage, brighter than warhead target